

EXPERIENTIAL LEARNING IN HANDICRAFT, TEACHERS' COMPETENCE AND STUDENTS' WORK SKILLS: BASIS FOR TLE SUPPLEMENTARY INSTRUCTIONAL MATERIAL

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ABSTRACT

Technology and Livelihood education are critical for the success of the 21st century workforce. This study aims to examine the Experiential Learning in Technology and Home Economics particularly in Handicraft, the competence of the teachers and their significant relationship on the Work Skills of the students in Balas Buco Sta. Maria National High School, Division of Batangas School year 2020-2021. To find out the output of the research study, the researcher utilized a self-made survey questionnaire which was administered to the respondents thru google forms with the helped of the subject teachers. Data were tested using different statistical tools such as frequency, mean, standard deviation and Spearman correlation. The salient findings of the study reveals that the respondents perceived all the related variables as Very Satisfactory such as, the Experiential Learning in Handicraft in terms of concrete experience, reflective observation, abstract conceptualization, and active experimentation; the teachers' competence in terms of strategies, teaching skills, monitoring system and evaluation skills; and the students work skills in terms of soft skills and hard skills. Findings also revealed that the Experiential Learning in Handicraft and Teachers Competencies are significantly related to the student respondents Work skills in terms of soft skills and hard skills. Furthermore, the hypothesis stating that the perceived experiential learning in handicraft and teachers' competencies has no significant relationship to the work skills of the students were not supported by the evidence, therefore rejected. This implies that experiential learning approaches are effective in teaching handicraft specifically in producing quality products in basketry, and macramé.

Keywords: TLE, Handicraft, Experiential learning, Teacher's Competence, Work Skills